

A FINITE DIFFERENCE TECHNIQUE FOR THE SOLUTION OF THIRD ORDER BOUNDARY VALUE PROBLEMS IN ORDINARY DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

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Abstract

In this paper, we propose an efficient finite difference method to solve third order boundary value problems. Analysis proves that the proposed method have at least quadratic convergence. Numerical results confirm the accuracy and efficiency of the proposed method.

Keywords: Boundary Value Problems, Finite Difference, Taylor series, Row Sum Norm, Maximum Error.

1. Introduction

Third-order differential equations arise in many modelling problems like aeroelasticity, beam deflection theory, electromagnetic waves, theory of thin film flow.

In this paper, we study an effective numerical technique based on finite differences to solve third order boundary value problems(BVPs) of the following type:

$$u''' = f(x, u), a \leq x \leq b \quad (1.1)$$

subject to the boundary conditions

$$u''(a) = \alpha, u\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) = \beta, u'(b) = \gamma \quad (1.2)$$

where the α , β and γ are arbitrary constants.

The discussion on the existence, uniqueness and convergence of the solution of problem 1.1 can be found in the literature [1], [12], [3], [6]. We wont mention the conditions on the existence and uniqueness of the solution to problem 1.1.

We assume the existence and uniqueness of the solution to problem 1.1. We also assume that problem 1.1 is well posed.

This article is arranged in the following order. In section 2, we propose the finite difference method. In section 3, we discuss the convergence of the proposed method. In section 4, we illustrate the method with examples and finally in section 5 we present the performance of our proposed method.

2. The Difference method

To find an approximation to the solution of the problem 1.1, we discretize the domain $[a, b]$ into N equal subintervals each of size $h = \frac{b-a}{N}$:

$$a = x_0 < x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_{N-1} < x_N = b \quad (2.1)$$

where the nodes are given by $x_i = a + ih, i = 0, 1, \dots, N$, where N is an even positive integer.

We want to determine the numerical approximation of the true solution $u(x)$ of the problem 1.1 at the nodal point

$$x_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

Let u_i and f_i denote the numerical approximations of $u(x)$ and $f(x, u(x))$ at $x = x_i, i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$ which allows us to write the boundary value problem 1.1 at node $x = x_i$ as written as

$$u_i''' = f_i, a \leq x_i \leq b \quad (2.2)$$

subject to the boundary conditions

$$u_0'' = \alpha, u_N = \beta, u_N' = \gamma, N \text{ even}$$

We define the nodes as

$$x_{i \pm \frac{1}{2}} = x_i \pm \frac{h}{2}, i = 1, 2, \dots, N - 1$$

and denote the solution of the problem 2.2 at $x_{i \pm \frac{1}{2}}$ by

$$u_{i \pm \frac{1}{2}}.$$

Using the method of undetermined coefficients and Taylor's series expansion [7, 8, 9], we get the following scheme:

and the b_i 's and T_i 's are given by

$$b_i = \begin{cases} h^2\alpha + \frac{h^3}{24}(25f_{\frac{1}{2}} + 11f_{\frac{3}{2}}) & \text{if } i = 1 \\ \frac{h^3}{2}(f_{\frac{1}{2}} + f_{\frac{3}{2}}) & \text{if } i = 2 \\ \vdots & \\ 8\beta - \frac{h^3}{16}(f_{\frac{N-3}{2}} - 9f_{\frac{N-1}{2}}) & i = \frac{N}{2} \\ \frac{h^3}{2}(f_{\frac{N-1}{2}} + f_{\frac{N+1}{2}}) & i = \frac{N}{2} + 1 \\ \vdots & \\ h\gamma + \frac{h^3}{48}(25f_{\frac{N-3}{2}} + 21f_{\frac{N-1}{2}}) & \text{if } i = N \end{cases} \quad (3.10)$$

and

$$T_i = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{24}h^5u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}^{(5)} & \text{if } i = 1 \\ \frac{1}{240}h^7u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}^{(7)} & \text{if } i = 2 \\ \vdots & \\ \frac{1}{16}h^5u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}^{(5)} & \text{if } i = \frac{N}{2} \\ \frac{1}{240}h^7u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}^{(7)} & \text{if } i = \frac{N}{2} + 1 \\ \vdots & \\ \frac{31}{1920}h^5u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}^{(5)} & \text{if } i = N \end{cases} \quad (3.11)$$

The matrix \mathbf{A} is nonsingular [4, 5] and its inverse $\mathbf{A}^{-1} = \mathbf{B} = [b_{ij}]$ is given by

$$b_{ij} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{8} & \text{if } i = M, i = 1, \dots, N \\ -\frac{(N-1)}{2} & \text{if } i = 1, j = N \\ \frac{(N-j+1)(N+1)}{2} & \text{if } i = 1, j = N - M + 1, N - M + 2, \dots, N - 1 \\ \frac{(2N^2+2N-7)}{8} & \text{if } i = 1, j = M - 1 \\ \vdots & \end{cases} \quad (3.12)$$

where $= \frac{N}{2}$, and

$$\|\mathbf{A}^{-1}\| \leq \frac{8N^3 - 3N^2 - 11N - 6}{48} \quad (3.13)$$

Here $\|\mathbf{A}^{-1}\|$ denotes the maximum row sum norm of \mathbf{A}^{-1} .

Now, for every even integer $N \geq 4$,

$$\|\mathbf{A}^{-1}\| \leq \frac{N^3}{6} \quad (3.14)$$

From equations 3.5 and 3.6, we have

$$\mathbf{Ae} = \mathbf{t} \quad (3.15)$$

which gives

$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{t} \quad (3.16)$$

Therefore,

$$\|\mathbf{e}\| \leq \|\mathbf{A}^{-1}\| \|\mathbf{t}\| \quad (3.17)$$

where $\|\mathbf{t}\|$ is the maximum norm of \mathbf{t} .

If we let,

$$M = \max_{a \leq x \leq b} |u^{(5)}(x)| \quad (3.18)$$

Then

$$\|\mathbf{t}\| \leq Mh^5 \quad (3.19)$$

Hence

$$\|\mathbf{e}\| \leq \frac{N^3 M h^5}{6} = \frac{(b-a)^3 M h^5}{6h^3} = \frac{M(b-a)^3}{6} h^2 \quad (3.20)$$

which shows that the our proposed scheme 2.3, 2.4 has second order convergence.

4. Numerical Examples

The following problems illustrate the performance of our method. We compute the maximum absolute error MAE in the true solution $u(x)$, namely:

$$\text{MAE} = \max_{0 \leq i \leq N} |u(x_i) - u_i|$$

All the computations were performed on Ubuntu 20.04.4 LTS GNU linux operating system with IDLE 3.8.10 running Python version 3.8.10 on Intel® Core™ i5-9400 CPU @ 2.90GHz × 6 PC.

Example 4.1. Consider the linear model problem in [10] given by:

$$u''' - xu(x) = (x^3 - 2x^2 - 5x - 3) \exp(x), 0 \leq x \leq 1 \quad (4.1)$$

with the boundary conditions

$$u''(0) = 0, u\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \frac{1}{4} \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), u'(1) = -\exp(1) \quad (4.2)$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = x(1-x)\exp(x) \quad (4.3)$$

The MAE computed by method 2.3 for different values of N are given below:

N	MAE
8	0.02033525883171955
16	0.00519953085188235
32	0.0013138297770312474
64	0.0003301567064563117
128	8.274841440109558e-05
256	2.0713042321846876e-05
512	5.181456980633825e-06
1024	1.295625032227913e-06
2048	3.2373742114572956e-07
4096	8.399874251030373e-08

Example 4.2. Consider the linear model problem in [11] given by:

$$u''' + u(x) = (x^2 - 6x - 1) \sin(x) + (7 - x^2) \cos x, 0 \leq x \leq 1, \quad (4.4)$$

with the boundary conditions

$$u''(0) = 0, u\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = -\frac{3}{4} \sin\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), u'(1) = 2\sin(1) \quad (4.5)$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = (x^2 - 1)\sin(x) \quad (4.6)$$

The MAE computed by method 2.3 for different values of N are given below:

N	MAE
8	0.01309914189714495
16	0.00313906340317055
32	0.0007675591677256399
64	0.00018974008936684106
128	4.716684442868102e-05
256	1.1758236153014412e-05
512	2.9353782288188413e-06
1024	7.333225403582944e-07
2048	1.8326568407278643e-07
4096	4.58072807463239e-08

Example 4.3. Consider the nonlinear model problem in [12] given by:

$$u''' + 2\exp(-3u(x)) = 4(1+x)^{-3}, 0 \leq x \leq 1, \quad (4.7)$$

with the boundary conditions

$$u''(0) = -1, u\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{3}{2}\right), u'(1) = \frac{1}{2} \quad (4.8)$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = \ln(1+x) \quad (4.9)$$

The MAE computed by method 2.3 for different values of N are given below:

N	MAE
8	0.001908417848461852
16	0.0004972795863560087
32	0.0001244093908235669
64	3.089767560763429e-05
128	7.68280713981783e-06
256	1.91441954876595e-06
512	4.778146070493795e-07
1024	1.1958167929156972e-07
2048	3.036098347931242e-08
4096	7.3120751675759266e-09

5. Conclusion

In this paper we have proposed a numerical method to solve third order boundary value problems having quadratic convergence. We have estimated the error involved. We have also given several numerical examples which confirms our claim.

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